

Quantum Impedance Network and its Power Distribution

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Abstract—In general unlike classical electrical circuits, power distribution within quantum impedance network is fundamentally different because power distribution is not only about voltage and current i.e, it also involves in energy transfer within particles and moreover, within quantum impedance networks because of interaction between particles, it considers interaction of elementary particles as impedance which governs flow of energy and quantum information.

Index Terms—Impedance, Sleep Wake cycle, Wavelengths, Electrical Pulses, Sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the field of engineering, general electrical(GE) is classified into two branches i.e, electrical engineering(EE) and secondly electrical instrumentation engineering(EIE). Basically in electrical engineering we deal with voltage and current but unlike classical electrical circuits, electrical instrumentation works on principles of Conductance, Inductance and finally Impedance which not only deals with voltage and current but also determines electrical energy within specified components.

II. INCLUSION OF ELECTRICAL IMPEDANCE WITHIN QUANTUM NEURAL NETWORKS

The concept of a quantum impedance networks is extended towards interaction of wavefunctions within particles, where impedance determines amplitude and phase of wavefunction within energy of particles. While considering neuro science terms and conditions, we assumed that in quantum neural networks with introduction of impedance, interaction of wavefunction within brain waves and its amplitude or phase is determined by wavelengths in sleep/wake cycle based on its patterns for selected subscriber.

III. APPLICATIONS SUPPORTED BY QUANTUM IMPEDANCE NETWORKS

Generally, we find many existing smart devices, for instance smart watch that senses heart rate through electrical pulses within our body, so here is my theory in day to day life i.e, 12 out 24 hours, we are naturally exposed to electrical energy by emission of light ignited by electrical circuits and moreover, in quantum impedance network, **electrical energy** comes into count unlike classical electrical circuits. Sensors in smart devices which captures electrical pulses determines amplitude of wave function through brain waves based

on wavelengths(alpha, theta, gamma, delta...) for computing sleep/wake cycle for verified patterns.

IV. CONCLUSION

Finally we conclude that, impedance plays vital role for applications supported by quantum impedance networks for computing Sleep wake cycles within progressive **Timelines**.